

Solar Energy Production : Environmental Impact in Rajasthan, India

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Abstract - Renewable energy technologies are gradually becoming popular throughout world including India. They play the pivotal role in case of sustainable development which takes care of growing energy demand of the modern civilization, but reducing the carbon emissions simultaneously which help to fight the climatic changes. Solar Energy is where the Sun's energy is collected and transformed to electrical energy through photovoltaic solar panels. Effective use of solar energy made a significant impact in the country's energy scenario in the past few decades. It was found that this practice particularly, by the common people of small towns and villages, in solar energy based different decentralized and distributed applications improved their standard of living as well as created job opportunities which ultimately was reflected in economic growth. In India, the world's biggest solar park is at Jodhpur, Rajasthan. Rajasthan receives little rainfall and due to its tropical desert climate, it is capable of producing huge amounts of solar energy. But there are potential hazards with negative environmental impacts of such renewable energy as well. This work aims to discuss the negative environmental impact of Solar energy production in Rajasthan, which at present is identified as a matter of concern.

Keywords - Solar; Renewable; Energy; Negative; Environmental Impact

1.0 Introduction

Due to industrialization, rapid growth in technology, consumption of energy is increasing globally in all sectors. In India, due to exponential population growth, the available energy is not sufficient [1]. Renewable energy of various forms are utilized to fill up such energy deficiencies. Here solar energy is becoming popular and playing the dominant role because of its various advantages. But the question arises in its sustainable character so far as environmental impact is concerned. Though solar energy is important in reducing emission of greenhouse gases with energy efficient output, the manufacturing, installation and transportation of solar panels are found to contribute a significant amount of carbon emission [2]. Land degradation and habitat loss are few other issues to be addressed seriously now for establishment of solar plants. It is found that regions having the highest solar energy potential must have dry climates, unused land mass with easy accessibility and most importantly, the regular availability of solar irradiance. So the state of Rajasthan, satisfying all such conditions has been chosen as a very promising destination for establishment of solar power production plants to contribute a major share in the estimated solar energy output of the country for overcoming the existing energy crisis [3]. But also there are environmental issues which need consideration as well.

2.0 India's Solar Energy Status

Solar energy is playing a major role in the country's National Action Plan on Climatic Change with the National Solar Mission being considered as a key mission. India has high potential for solar energy production. The National Institute of Solar Energy has predicted India's solar potential to be about 748 GW with a projected estimation of nearly 3% of the unused land area to be covered by Solar photovoltaic modules. The generated solar photovoltaic power can be harnessed effectively to provide very high scalability here. Solar tariff is made competitive presently to support the sustainable growth agenda of the country and has emerged as an essential part of the solution to meet the nation's energy needs. As on 30th November, 2022, installed capacity of India's solar power has reached around 61.97 GW. Around 5,000 trillion kWh/year of the Sun's energy is incident over India's land area where most parts receive (4-7) kWh/sq. m/day on average [4].

3.0. Rajasthan in Solar Energy Sector : Its policies and positive impact

But Rajasthan emerged as the front runner when conversion of the Sun's optical energy to electrical output is considered.

Being India's largest state and located in the north-western section of the country, Rajasthan harbors massive Thar Desert. Naturally it has a dry climate having few cloudy days which are unsuitable for farming making it perfect for generation of solar power. It reduces greenhouse gas emissions improving air quality, thus mitigating climate change which is critical for protection of not only the human, but for the wildlife and their ecosystems also. It is important to mention here that solar power-producing systems and plants in these less inhabited areas of Rajasthan allow clean energy to reach those isolated communities which do not have access to electricity, but not at the cost of environmental sustainability.

The relevant data for Rajasthan solar energy status is shown in Table 1 [5,6].

Solar generation potential	142 GW
Installed Capacity Target set by 2024-25	30 GW
Solar radiation capture	6-7 kWh/sq. m /day
No. of available sunny days/ year at	300, 27.0238° N, 74.2179° E
Installed Capacity as on 30 th June, 2022	14.45 GW

Table 1 Data for Rajasthan's Solar Energy Production

Additionally, the state government's solar policy aids to provide necessary support for the solar sector to expand. It consists of infrastructural support as well as allowances for lucrative concessions for such projects which are demanding sector wise burgeoning too.

Rajasthan's residents, under the pan-India Rooftop Solar Program Phase II scheme, as launched by the Ministry of New & Renewable Energy, can avail for their rooftop solar, central financial assistance (CFA) as solar energy subsidy for residential solar consumers and housing societies [7].

The Rajasthan Investment Promotion Scheme (RIP) 2019 and other measures created an investment-friendly environment as the state government has designated entire renewable energy including solar energy as a priority sector with some special benefit. There is the

provision for employment subsidy [8].

State Goods and Services Tax (SGST) subsidy is also provided for solar, wind, and hybrid energy production equipment (Table 2).

Sl. No.	Scheme	The system & the benefit
1.	Pan-India Rooftop Solar Program Phase II scheme	Rooftop solar subsidy upto 3 kWp : 40% of the benchmark cost (3- 10) kWp : 20% of benchmark cost upto 500 kWp: 20% of the benchmark cost @Rs.14,588/- per kW
2.	Rajasthan Investment Promotion Scheme	Renewable Energy Stamp duty and Land tax exemption: 100 % for the 1 st 7 years Employment subsidy 50 %
3.	State Goods and Services Tax	Energy equipment production subsidy 90 %

Table 2 Rajasthan Government's subsidy policy for Solar Power production

Above two considerations when compounded together, resulted in favorable situation which made possible to build world's largest solar park, the Bhadla Solar Park at Jodhpur district of Rajasthan which was commissioned in 2022 and spread over a total area of 5,700 hectares (14,000 acres) with installed capacity of 2245 MW [9].

4.0 Rajasthan's Solar Energy : Environmental Issues

It is known that solar energy is an alternative clean energy source as it does not produce any harmful emissions or by-products which could harm the environment and the corresponding ecosystem. The storage batteries are also very safe as they are free of emissions. So to go green with solar power systems along with solar batteries is highly favored in the reduction of carbon footprints. But solar energy is produced using photovoltaic panels whose production procedure is commonly associated with various toxic wastes, unsustainable mining practices, habitat loss, and most importantly carbon emissions and so the consequences of solar panel manufacturing effect needs some discussion as these are related to the solar energy future.

4.1 Solar Panel Production, Waste Generation & Discharge of Pollutants

Photovoltaic (PV) panel production is resource-intensive and requires hazardous chemicals and even fossil fuels. Coal is used here as primary energy source which is responsible for the increased carbon emissions.

Hydrofluoric acid (HF) and sodium hydroxides (NaOH) are used in the solar panel manufacturing processes which require strict regulations regarding the treatment and disposal of toxic waste water.

Studies show that [10] silicon particles are released into the environment during the production

process which may cause Silicosis to the people coming in contact with the particles.

So PV cells and panels must be carefully handled to avoid release of such emissions to the environment. So for the workers working at photovoltaic panel production units, proper safety measures are the important priority to be taken through regulated protections.

Also though solar panels are mainly made out of glass, some types of PV cell technologies use heavy metals like cadmium and lead, which are classified as carcinogenic [11]. To recycle these components after the end of their life, additional costs must be allocated to remove these. So present practice is to discharge them in landfills where cadmium may be released and washed out with rainwater leaching into the soil and polluting the surrounding area.

Presently in India, approximately 200,000 tons of solar photovoltaic waste are expected to be produced by 2030 and 1.8 million tons by 2050, by which time solar waste could grow to 60 million tons globally. Solar waste has recently been included in the category of waste electrical and electronic equipment to restrict the negative influence of continual development [12].

4.2 Environmental Hazards of Mining

Photovoltaic panels utilize more than 19 of the rare minerals in modern manufacturing processes [13]. These are mined at various locations around the world. The demand for these minerals is very high to improve solar energy production by meeting the consumers' demand for new technology.

Study reveals that due to this huge demand, enough Indium, a component for photovoltaic panels is not available to supply for this green revolution. So mining is needed which is a matter of concern as mining results in loss of biodiversity and contamination of nearby water streams from highly acidic metal waste.

4.3 Land Use and Thermal Pollution

Solar photovoltaics are related to the specific factor of the area and the topography of land that would be covered, sensitive ecosystems, and biodiversity. The application of the solar cells in cultivable land is discouraged as it may harm the land's productivity. Large-scale utilization of the land also affects thermal balance of the area by absorbing more energy by the earth, otherwise energy would be reflected by the surface back to space. Rajasthan's solar power application utilizes square kilometers of desert area affecting largely the thermal balance of this land space. Also, additional heat might destroy a few species living in this kind of harsh environment.

4.4 Habitat Loss

With high solar irradiance, Rajasthan's Thar desert is considered ideal for solar power. But action plans for future expansion of solar installations have been considered to come at the cost of existing village commons, locally called orans [14]. Arid Forest Research Institute (AFRI), under the Union Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change identified them as the richest biodiversity in the deserts featuring not only the water body and grazing cows, sheep, and goats, but these are home to the endangered great Indian bustard (GIB), chinkara, and the Indian desert fox. These lands are now under threat as they are considered to be used for generating the green energy solar.

The Supreme Court verdict of 2018 instructed to protect the orans as deemed forests. But in the last few years orans have either been handed over to green energy companies or been

encroached upon by power grids and lines installed by these companies. These power lines had caused the death of not only GIBs but also of the laggar falcon and other such endangered species. So the highest court order should be obeyed by all concerned to protect the oran environment and its biodiversity.

5.0 Conclusion

With the correct investments in green innovations, India is ready to accomplish sustainable power targets. Rajasthan is one of the leading states that pursue cleaner energy which is an essential function in empowering the nation's change to a completely supportable energy framework. Advancements in renewable energy in India will create jobs for locale, rural electrification and promote electric mobility too. But there are many challenges in utilizing renewable energy such as a mismatch in supply-demand, lack of financial support for the high initial cost of off-grid applications, risk perception, lack of policies for developer's credit.

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